

**THE EFFECT OF WORK CLIMATE AND WORK DISCIPLINE ON
EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE
(STUDY ON ONE OF THE 3 STAR HOTELS IN BANDUNG)**

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Abstract

This research conducted with the aim to determine the effect of work climate and work discipline on employee performance and this study also aims to analyze the most dominant factors of influence between work climate and work discipline on employee performance. The object of his research was that 87 employees used a questionnaire aimed at employees registered at one of the 3-star hotels in the city of Bandung.

Based on research using path analysis, it can be seen that the working climate variable (X_1) has a direct influence of 24.1%, indirect influence through relations with work discipline (X_2) of 14.3%, the total effect of 38.4%. Work discipline variables (X_2) have a direct influence of 15.3%, and indirect effects through work motivation (X_1) are 14.3%, the total effect is 29.6%. The results of the correlation coefficient of determination (R squared) expressed in percentages illustrate the contribution of all independent variables namely work motivation (X_1) and work discipline (X_2) in determining the performance variable is 0.679 or 67.9% while other factors that affect performance not examined indicated by the value of 0.321 or 32.1%. The conclusions of the suggestions that can be considered in connection with the results of the study are that management should be able to maintain and improve the two variables above.

Keywords: *Work Climate, Work Discipline, Employee Performance.*

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INTRODUCTION

Companies must be able to manage their employees and improve performance by expectations. Productivity that can meet company targets is a reflection of the level of functional or not employee performance. Good employee performance with a good work ethic will undoubtedly help the company to gain profits and vice versa, and employee performance will cause losses to the company. Thus managing employees must be able to be realized by management. The high level of employee loyalty and achievement of company targets will be able to be achieved by the company.

HR has an active and dominant role in every activity of the company because of humans as planners, executors, and evaluators of the condition of the company towards the realization of organizational goals. This condition requires management efforts to improve the performance of its employees. Employee performance is how much their contribution to the company basically what employees must and should not do.

Efforts to improve performance to achieve goals are not impossible. One of the efforts made by management is to provide conducive working conditions and affirmation of rules. Rules and discipline are other points of concern to management because the success of the company depends on its employees. The efficiency of the company will not be achieved well if the employee does not have adherence to the rules that apply in the company. Improving discipline can improve employee performance, which impacts on improving company efficiency. Discipline also needs to be safeguarded to win the market and increase consumers' positive views of the

company's image, especially for service companies.

The hotel is a company that contains elements of service in the form of accommodation and accommodation and other services regarding the needs of consumers both dishes and comfort facilities as well as security following public facilities that are the comfort, privacy, and commercial. Tangible and intangible facilities support each other and are mutually sustainable so that it has an essential role for the company to seize the opportunity and win the competition. This cause indeed demands the quality of qualified human resources.

To realize the company's vision and mission to become a superior hotel in all aspects, it can achieve by improving the quality of its people to be better and to manage employees optimally. It is not only limited to creating service values but also further evaluating shortcomings and maximizing company excellence. The phenomenon found by researchers is the lack of a favorable work climate in the Hotel environment. An unfavorable work climate can affect employee motivation that results in a decrease in employee performance.

As a company engaged in tourism has a dynamic work climate, and consumers differ from each other, it requires creativity and resilience of employees to face work every day. The workload burden ultimately makes employees reluctant to increase their productivity and are at a stagnant level of performance. Communication sought by the management often does not produce a good solution. Employees feel dissatisfied with their work and think that the work climate is not conducive.

The problem because it is not only a loss for the employee, but the company is also a loss for the company because to find and train new workers requires a lot of time and money. The expected performance cannot achieve if the work environment is comfortable and the conditions of employees often change. The performance results achieved by employees are a concern of Hotel management. Various policies and efforts to improve performance have been carried out, but it felt that it has not been able to reach the expected company targets, s shows that employee performance is not optimal. The factors that cause this decline must be able to be identified so that they can become the basis for making decisions in the next period.

Performance influenced by several factors such as those described by Siagian (2013) mentioning performance as a result of work achieved by a person in carrying out his duties where it depends on skills, experience, sincerity, and accuracy both in terms of time and quality, as well as individual motivation. Performance is also the result or level of success of a person as a whole over a while in carrying out tasks compared to the various possibilities of work results, targets or targets or criteria that have been determined in advance and agreed upon are a form of performance (Rivai, 2014).

Also presented by Mangkunegara (2011) that work performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties according to the responsibilities given to him. Thus, performance is an essential thing for the organization or company and from the employee's side. Therefore, the performance will run well if supported by motivation and work discipline.

The low work climate of employees causes a decrease in service quality and timeliness of employees and results in the lack of quality performance of the work performed by employees. Performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization, following the authority and responsibilities

of each, to achieve the objectives of the organization concerned legally, not violating the law and following morals and ethics. Various factors including mental attitude fulfil the work performed by employees, work motivation, work discipline, and work ethics, education and training, skills, management, relationships between employees, ideology, leadership attitudes, income levels, to physical factors such as nutrition and health, social security, environment and work climate, production facilities, technology level and opportunities for achievement. Work climate is one of the factors that significantly determines the performance of the company (Moorhead & Griffin, 2013)

In addition to the work climate, variable work discipline is also a problem for hotel management. The researcher found several employees who made negligence on job responsibilities. The inaccuracy of time accumulated illustrates the lack of optimal discipline applied in this company. The implication is that it is not appropriate to complete the work according to the quantity that should be.

Wirawan (2015) explains that discipline is the attitude and behavior of compliance with regulations, both work procedures, codes of ethics, and other organizational policies that must obey. The discipline of whether or not an employee will affect the quality of the product produced and affect the quality of services provided to consumers.

Sutrisno (2011) state that the better the work discipline of an employee, the higher the work results that will achieve. With the implementation of discipline, it expected that employees could be aware of the rules, both for regulators and employees at the most basic level. It is likely that with the application of discipline from all employees, the performance will be more optimal.

Based on the existing problems, the formulation of the problem to be investigated is: the influence of the work climate and work discipline on employee performance both simultaneously and partially. The purpose of the study is to determine the magnitude of the importance

of the work climate and work discipline on Employee Performance both simultaneously and partially.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Wahjosumidjo (2010) states that goals can achieve if employees are motivated by work condition, one of which is to improve work discipline. Seriousness in work which is one form of motivation reflected in the obedience and obedience of employees to company rules. The purpose of the higher motivation is to stabilize and reduce absenteeism and enhance employees' sense of responsibility towards their duties. Arep & Tanjung (2008) states that work motivation can be measured based on employee responsibilities in fulfilling the implementation of their commitments and this can be seen from the timeliness and discipline of employees. These theories explicitly state the relationship between work climate and work motivation. Work climate is more crucial than organizational skills or techniques in creating an effective organization. Positive observation can help develop the desired response more likely to affect organizational relationships that are more pleasant than unpleasant. Work climate is a human environment where employees do work and will influence their behavior in an organization that is often described as an organizational culture so that it has implications for the performance of employees in carrying out their work.

Furthermore, it can say that the work climate affects the performance of employees seen in doing good work as revealed by Subramani, Akbar Jan, Moideen Batha & Vinodh (2016) there is a correlation between the climate of the organization and employee performance. Organizational climate can define as a set of measurable traits of an

organizational environment based on the collective perception of people who live and work the importance of an organizational climate that supports increasing organizational performance.

Sutrisno (2011) suggests the relationship between work discipline and the results of employee performance where he states that: "The better the work discipline of an employee, the higher the results of work will be achieved." The mental attitude that encourages employees to strive to achieve work performance to the maximum. Discipline defined as the willingness of someone who arises with his awareness to follow the rules that apply in the organization. Work discipline is realized by adhering to and implementing company policies in the work environment in the form of norms, codes of ethics, or time. Discipline is one of the essential factors in an organization. It is said to be a necessary factor because work discipline will affect employee performance in the organization. The higher the employee's work discipline, the more optimal the performance of the employee and its impact will help the organization achieve the company's vision and mission.

Looking at previous studies that have examined the interrelationships between variables and based on explanations, the hypothesis in this study is that there is an influence of work climate and work discipline on employee performance both simultaneously and partially.

METHODS

Based on the variables to be studied, the method of this research is descriptive and verification research. Verification research is used to determine the effect of the variables examined on other variables, namely independent variables and dependent variables intended to test

hypotheses using statistical methods, knowing the truth of a hypothesis through processing data obtained from respondents — this research conducted at one of the 3-star Hotels in the City for four months. Respondents were Hotel employees as many as 87 people. Sampling uses simple random sampling. Operational variables consist of three variables, namely:

1. Independent Variables

The independent variable is a variable that affects other variables or variables that are thought to be the cause of other variables. Concerning the problem under study, the independent variable is the work climate stated by Sutrisno (2011) which is a work climate that is an internal psychological environment of an organization that is perceived and felt by employees which affect the behavior of the next employee so that it is the specific organization with other organizations. (Jyoti, 2013) And Discipline as stated by Subramani, Akbar Jan, Moideen Batha & Vinodh (2016) which is a condition that causes or encourages employees to act and do all activities by established norms/regulations.

2. Dependent Variables

Non-independent variables are variables that are affected or that are due to the existence of independent variables. Concerning the problem under study, the non-free variable is employee performance which is expressed by Siagian (2013) which is the work of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties by the responsibilities given to him.

To find out the relationship and influence between the research variables used the technique of Path Analysis. Path analysis is also called regression

analysis, a relationship pattern that shows the close relationship between variables or correlation patterns of relationships that reveal the influence of a set of other variables. Research that uses the structure of relationships between causal variables and the following variables to prove the proposed hypothesis.

RESEARCH RESULT

In doing path analysis, there is a requirement that must meet, namely the existence of a relationship or correlation between variables in all the independent variables involved. In this study, it means that there must be a relationship or correlation between variables X1 and X2. The correlation coefficient value indicates the relationship between these variables.

Calculation of correlation analysis between these variables was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment correlation, namely to find out how strong the relationship between independent variables in this study. For this purpose, a device used in the form of SPSS software. The results of the relationship between work climate variables (X1) with work discipline variables (X2) obtained a value of 0.744, so that if interpreted with an interpretation table value (correlation), then it has a high level of relationship (because the value of $r > 0.70 - 0.90$) and in the same direction (because r is positive).

Because it has a significant number of $0.000 < 0.01$. Means that if the work climate variable (X1) rises by one unit, then the work discipline variable (X2) rises by 0.744 or vice versa. Path analysis is used to determine the contribution of the independent variables

(X1 and X2) to the dependent variable (Y). The influence referred to here is the direct and indirect influence of each of these variables. The value of the path coefficients indicates the magnitude of the contribution of the impact of each variable in each of these variables. The results of path analysis through linear regression analysis that exist in the SPSS software in this study is where the X1 variable has a path coefficient of 0.491, and the X2 variable has a path coefficient of 0.391. So that the path equation obtained is:

$$Y = 0,491(X1) + 0,391(X2) + \varepsilon$$

Where :

X1 = Work climate

X2 = Work Discipline

Y = Performance

ε = Variables that are not examined or measured but affect performance.

From the equation above, it can be interpreted that every increase in work climate (X1) is one unit, it will increase performance (Y) by 0.491 units, and each increase in work discipline (X2) is one unit will improve performance (Y) by 0.391 units.

While the magnitude of the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable both direct impact and indirect influence that the work climate variable (X1) has a direct influence of 24.1%, indirect influence through its relationship with work discipline (X2) of 14.3 %, and the total effect is 38.4%.

The work discipline variable (X2) has a direct influence of 15.3%, the indirect effect through its relationship with the work climate (X1) is 14.3% so that the

total result is 29.6%. And produce a simultaneous influence of 67.9%.

Simultaneously to determine the magnitude of the contribution of independent variables to changes in the dependent variable obtained from the coefficient of determination. The results of the contribution of work climate variables (X1) and work discipline (X2) against employee performance (Y) amounted to 67.9% while the remaining only 32.1% is the contribution of other variables that are not careful and also influence Employee Performance (Y) indicated by the value 0.321 or equal to 32.1%.

The hypothesis testing is passively observed from the t-test while simultaneous hypothesis testing seen from table F or ANOVA. Based on the results obtained from the ratio of Fcount to Ftable, Ho rejected because Fcount $88.885 \geq$ (F table 3.10) art has a significant effect. Whereas the test based on the results obtained from the comparison of t count with t table is H0 rejected because the working climate variable, t count $5.305 \geq$ t table 1.988 then Ho is rejected and the Work Discipline variable, t count $4.230 \geq$ t table 1.988 then Ho is rejected means significant effect.

DISCUSSION

After analyzing the respondent's answer, the next step the researcher needs to do an in-depth discussion about the conditions and phenomena related to the research variables, both descriptively and verificative. As is known together with the aspects of the work climate, and work discipline and is the main factor that drives employee performance, therefore we need to inventory the

dominant elements that are determined by employee performance.

This study tries to reveal the work climate and work discipline on employee performance. Furthermore, for the next researcher, it is proven that employee performance influenced by work climate and work discipline. But of course, this research is still not perfect because there are still many other factors that can affect performance.

According to Subramani, Akbar Jan, Moideen Batha & Vinodh (2016) argue that organizational climate is a particular characteristic that distinguishes an organization from other organizations and influences the behavior of people in the organization. Work climate is a human environment where employees do work, and this understanding can refer to the climate of departments, essential companies, or an organization as a whole, the work climate will affect their behavior in organizations often described as an organizational culture that has implications for employee performance. The research conducted by Jyoti (2013) proves that the existence of a pleasant work climate will improve work-related performance. Thus the study undertaken by Bamel, Rangnekar, Stokes & Rastogi (2013) demonstrates that the existence of a conducive work climate can increase management effectiveness. Furthermore, Agarwal (2015) proved that the work climate is mediation in improving performance.

Based on the opinion of Malinen & Savolainen (2016), there is a relationship between discipline and work-related outcome. Beyer & Trice (1984) prove that discipline is one of the controls in determining someone's performance. Gilbert, De Winne & Sels (2011) and Lawrence, Ott & Bell (2012) prove their

research that discipline is an outcome of commitment that has implications for individual behavior. The mental attitude that drives employees to try to achieve work performance to the fullest. Discipline defined as a person's willingness to arise with his awareness to follow the rules that apply in the organization.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The description of the Work climate can be described quite well with an average value of 2.61 with a total overall score of 3.404. The overall picture of work discipline can be explained quite well with an average value of 2.61 with a total overall score of 2.896. The overall performance picture can be drawn on reasonably well with an average value of 2.77 with a total overall score of 3,616. The work climate provides the most dominant contribution to Employee Performance with a total influence of 38%. Work discipline provides a lower contribution to Employee Performance with an overall impact of 29%. Simultaneously the work climate and work discipline affect 67% of Employee Performance. While other factors are not examined and also influence Employee Performance as indicated by the value $\rho_{y\epsilon} = 0.321$ or 32%. Other factors in question are leadership, work environment, compensation, and other variables as written in identifying problems.

In improving the work climate the need for management to pay attention to the willingness of employees to evaluate and improve their work that is not optimal so that optimal employee performance can be achieved and the company's goals can be realized properly. Improve and enhance the role of individual workers to have the desire to influence their work

environment. To maintain and improve work discipline the management should emphasize the rules and provide appropriate sanctions so that employees keep their level of absenteeism and can fulfill their obligations in completing the given work.

Overall, the positive contribution of the work climate and work discipline has a significant impact on employee performance. Therefore management must be able to maintain and improve the performance that has been achieved at this time for the sustainability of the company and to realize the company's goals. Further improvement in employee performance is not only focused on the work climate and work discipline alone, but the management must also again strive to identify and process other factors that are capable of causing employee performance fluctuations. The management must be able to do this, of course, to realize the company's performance at the maximum level.

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